

Sum of Divisors Function

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published online: 15 July 2023	We show that the recurrence relation deduced by Robbins and Osler et al for the sum of divisors function $\sigma(n)$ can be solved in terms of the complete Bell polynomials. Besides, the connection between $\sigma(2n + 1)$ and the number of representations of n as the sum of four triangular numbers allows obtain arecurrence relation where only participate the values of $\sigma(m)$ with m odd.
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1.- INTRODUCTION

In [1] were considered recurrence relations with the structure of a Cauchy convolution [2]:

$$n f_k(n) = \sum_{j=1}^n h(j) f_k(n-j), \quad k \geq 1, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

verifying the properties $f_k(0) = 1 \quad \forall k$ and $h(0) = 0$, where it was used the Z- transform to obtain the following solution:

$$f_k(n) = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(0! h(1), 1! h(2), 2! h(3), \dots, (n-1)! h(n)), \quad (2)$$

in terms of the complete Bell polynomials [3-9].

In Sec. 2 we observe that the Robbins [10] – Osler et al [11-13] identity for the sum of divisors function $\sigma(n)$ [2] has the structure (1), hence it is applicable the result (2). In Sec. 3 it is used the connection between $\sigma(m)$ and $t_4(N)$, that is, the number of representations of N as a sum of 4 triangular numbers [14, 15], to deduce an interesting recurrence relation involving only the values of $\sigma(m)$ with m odd.

2.- OSLER et al – ROBBINS IDENTITY

We know the following recurrence relation [10-13] with the structure (1):

$$n a_n = - \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma(j) a_{n-j}, \quad a_0 = 1, \quad \sigma(0) = 0, \quad n \geq 1, \quad (3)$$

where [16]:

$$a_j = \begin{cases} 0, & j \neq \frac{m}{2}(3m+1), \\ (-1)^m, & j = \frac{m}{2}(3m+1), \end{cases} \quad m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \quad (4)$$

that is:

$$a_j = \begin{cases} 1, & j = 0, 5, 7, 22, 26, 51, 57, 92, 100, 145, 155, \dots \\ -1, & j = 1, 2, 12, 15, 35, 40, 70, 77, 117, 126, 176, \dots \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

hence (2) implies the closed expression:

$$a_n = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(-0! \sigma(1), -1! \sigma(2), -2! \sigma(3), \dots, -(n-1)! \sigma(n)), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (6)$$

and its corresponding inversion is given by:

$$\sigma(n) = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{j=1}^n (-1)^k (k - 1)! B_{n,k}(1! a_1, 2! a_2, \dots, (n-k+1)! a_{n-k+1}), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (7)$$

in terms of the partial Bell polynomials.

3.- RECURRENCE RELATION FOR $\sigma(m)$ WITH m ODD

In [12] it was obtained the following recurrence relation:

$$n t_k(n) = -k \sum_{j=1}^n j T(j) t_k(n-j), \quad (8)$$

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where $t_k(n)$ is the number of representations of n as a sum of k triangular numbers, and:

$$T(j) = \sum_{d|j} \frac{1+2(-1)^d}{d} = \frac{1}{j} \sum_{d|j} (-1)^d d. \tag{9}$$

On the other hand, we have the connection [14, 15]:

$$t_4(n) = \sigma(2n + 1), \tag{10}$$

then (10) and (8) with $k = 4$ imply the relation:

$$n \sigma(2n + 1) = -4 \sum_{j=1}^n j T(j) \sigma(2n + 1 - 2j), \tag{11}$$

$$n \geq 0,$$

as an alternative recurrence to (3); we note that into (11) only participate the values of $\sigma(m)$ with m odd. We know that any positive integer can be written in the form $n = 2^k m$, $k \geq 0$ such that m is odd, therefore:

$$\sigma(n) = (2^{k+1} - 1) \sigma(m), \tag{12}$$

hence all values of the sum of divisors function are generated by the quantities $\sigma(m)$, where m is odd, which are determined using (11).

Similarly, we have the result of Ewell [17, 18]:

$$t_2(n) = \frac{1}{4} r_2(4n + 1), \tag{13}$$

where $r_2(n)$ is the number of representations of n as a sum of two squares [19-21], thus (13) and (8) with $k = 2$ imply the recurrence relation:

$$n r_2(4n + 1) = -2 \sum_{j=1}^n j T(j) r_2(4n + 1 - 4j), \tag{14}$$

$$n \geq 0,$$

which is a companion expression for the following formula obtained in [12]:

$$n r_2(n) = -4 \sum_{j=1}^n (-1)^j j D(j) r_2(n - j), \tag{15}$$

$$D(j) = \sum_{\text{odd } d|j} \frac{1}{d}, \quad n \geq 0.$$

Remark 1: The recurrence relation (3) can be written in the form [10]:

$$\sigma(n) + \sum_{k \geq 1} (-1)^k [\sigma(n - \omega(k)) + \sigma(n - \omega(-k))] = \begin{cases} (-1)^{m-1} n, & \text{if } n = \omega(\pm m), \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

where $\omega(k) = \frac{k}{2}(3k - 1)$ are the pentagonal numbers.

Remark2: Gandhi [12, 22, 23] deduced the following recurrence relation for the colour partitions $p_k(n)$ [13, 24, 25]:

$$n p_r(n) = -r \sum_{r=1}^n \sigma(r) p_r(n - r), \quad r, n \geq 1, \tag{17}$$

where we can employ $r = 1$ to obtain (3) because $p_1(n) = a_n$; furthermore, letting $r = -1$ in (17) gives the well-known expression [13]:

$$n p(n) = \sum_{j=1}^n \sigma(j) p(n - j), \tag{18}$$

involving the partition function.

Remark 3: The property (7) implies the following determinant [4, 25]:

$$\sigma(n) = \begin{vmatrix} na_n & a_1 & a_2 & a_3 & \dots & a_{n-1} \\ (n-1)a_{n-1} & 1 & a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_{n-2} \\ (n-2)a_{n-2} & 0 & 1 & a_1 & \dots & a_{n-3} \\ \vdots & 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 2a_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & a_1 \\ a_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{vmatrix}, \quad n \geq 1. \tag{19}$$

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